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COVER PAGE AND DECLARATION

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Introduction

As stated by (*Ethical Considerations in Data Science: Privacy and Bias / MoldStud, 2024*), “The field of data science has experienced exponential growth, driven by technological advancements and the vast amounts of data generated by individuals and organizations. Its applications span across various sectors, from healthcare and finance to marketing and consumer insights. With the advent of artificial intelligence and machine learning, data science has gained the ability to forecast trends, predict behavior, and make data-driven decisions that drive business success. However, this rapid growth and reliance on data also raise concerns about privacy and ethical considerations. As data scientists delve into personal data, they must navigate a fine line between innovation and privacy invasion. Organizations must prioritize privacy and implement robust ethical frameworks to protect individuals' sensitive information.” The project.io (*Ethical Considerations in Data Science, 2024*) is also stated, “Data ethics is crucial to safeguard privacy, prevent discrimination, and ensure accountability in data usage. It establishes trust, upholds fairness, and mitigates risks associated with data collection, analysis, and dissemination, fostering responsible and ethical practices in an increasingly data-driven world.”

Objective of this report is researching on a selected ethical or legal issue related to data science, and provide an analysis of the issue and potential solutions to mitigate any negative impacts. So, this research entitled “Ethical and Legal Issues Related to Smart City in Cambodia.” to examines the ethical and legal issues associated with the use of smart city in Cambodia with marking criteria including research and analysis, ethical considerations and legal consideration.

Main Body

1. Research and Analysis

1.1. Comprehensive understanding of Smart City

Based on Shea and Burns (2020), “A smart city is a municipality that uses information and communication technologies (ICT) to increase operational efficiency, share information with the public and improve both the quality of government services and citizen welfare. While the exact definition varies, the overarching mission of a smart city is to optimize city functions and drive

economic growth while improving quality of life for its citizens using smart technology and data analysis. Value is given to the smart city based on what they choose to do with the technology, not just how much technology they may have. Several major characteristics are used to determine a city's smartness. These characteristics include: a technology-based infrastructure; environmental initiatives; a high functioning public transportation system; a confident sense of urban planning and humans to live and work within the city and utilize its resources.” In actual implementation of smart city, the repsol.com website wrote about five smartest cities in the world by reference from IMD Smart City Index 2021 including first a small country of ASIAN is Singapore, second is Zurich, a city in Switzerland, third is Oslo from Norway, fourth. Taipei, a capital city of Taiwan (Republic of China) and fifth is Lausanne, also in Switzerland (*What Is a Smart City? (With Examples | Repsol, 2023)*). Even though Cambodia is still a developing country, but Cambodia try to evolve itself to smart city. Firstly, there is a Phnom Penh Master Plan 2035 of smart city concept to develop Phnom Penh city to become one of start city. By CHANNARITH (2023) “As Cambodia's capital and largest city, Phnom Penh is also its most populated. Phnom Penh is in the south-central region of Cambodia, and fully surrounded by the Kandal province. Phnom Penh has an area of 692.46 square kilometres. The autonomous municipality is subdivided into 14 administrative divisions called khans (sections). The districts are subdivided into 105 sangkats and further subdivided into 953 phums (villages). As of 2023, Phnom Penh had a population of 2,281,000 people. Public transport modes have been introduced and expanded: public bus services from 2014 and water taxi services since 2018.” Secondly, Siem Reap Province in Cambodia that has Angkor Word Heritage is transforming to smart city by 2035 aims to improve well-being of the local people and community and enhance accommodation for high number of tourists. This project handles by Japanese International Cooperation Agency (JICA) with more than 18 million of budget (*Siem Reap ‘Smart City’ Goal on Track for 2035, 2023*).

1.2. In-Depth analysis of the issue and its potential impacts

Major Issues in Cambodia to become the smart city are Cambodia needs to manage, examine, improve all details of the master plan. Implement the many coordination processes and plans necessary for intelligent and harmonious development on an ongoing basis. It is required to improve safety for pedestrians on sidewalk or waking paths in public areas. Increasing the

number of vehicles in the city, which causes pollution and harms citizens' health so traffic needs to improve the optimized management in the capital to reduce congestion and pollution. Developing more global shared mobility applications to ease for public transportation. Safe transportation, travel and excursions are important and should be strengthened in Phnom Penh. Providing high quality services to citizens such a good waste collection schedules platform. More over CCTV cameras should be installed on roads to ensure people's privacy and safety. Improving parking lots in the inappropriate place must be considered to reduce traffic jams, etc. Requiring of better driving mapping layout in certain locations (one way lane, connection roads, etc.) to reduce wasting time for packing lot. Forecasting platform for a smart safety system (fire, pollution, pandemic, etc.) is the most requirement for smart city.

1.3. Identification of potential solutions

Several issues and its potential impacts have been addressed including safety for pedestrians, safe and easy transportation, smart traffic, waste collection schedule, CCTV camera, driving mapping layout or forecasting platform. Identification of the potential solutions of smart city in Cambodia are: Encourage on startup technology researching from public and private sector based on the issues and solutions; strong encouragement for open data for the development of innovative technologies to achieve intelligent living find supporters or prepare financial supports to provide budgets on technology innovation and enhancement; public encourage and promote to all education and technical institutions to design curriculum and teach courses related to technology especially smart city; deeply encourage on advance technology development such as IoT (Internet of Things) and AI (Artificial Intelligence). Smart Phnom Penh, a Capital City that uses information & technology to better respond sustainably to its community and business needs by planning to develop five main priority areas including Land usage, Safety and Security, Urban Mobility, Environment, and Digital Management. Land usage in the Phnom Penh city requires a digital map to visualize detailed accurate vision of the layout of the city and physical infrastructure. Safety and security are improved for citizens, pedestrian, or transported vehicle in public space by installing many CCTV cameras with digitally monitored from a distance. The objectives of Urban Mobility include convenient mobility, safe trips, smart parking or accessible public transport usage. The detailed of the Environment are improved such as waste collection management, climate forecasting to manage disasters when they will occur. The citizens are

needed them to notify the disasters before it actual happen. Digital management of the smart city are announcement and promoting digital knowledge to all parties such as government and citizen. Make sure they can use digital awareness to exchange information either government to government and government to citizen.

2. Ethical Considerations

2.1. Ethical considerations related to Smart City

Smart city uses many kinds of technology to give a lot of advantages to citizens. How ever it also become dangerous technology if there were no highly consideration and management. Security and privacy protection are the most difficult issues that smart city must address. Big data must be stored to smart city processing is large, various types, and complexity and it also open and transparent data communicate to each other across the country. This matter can be faced with cyber attacks that can breach of user's data privacy pose risks and harms to individual or even the government. If there is a leak of breach occur, it will give confidence that the use of technology can lead to untrust to use because of fear of affecting their daily lives. So data storage of individual and government must be stored and managed by highly knowledge of IT engineers to protect from breach of user's data privacy. In the A case like this was reported in 2018, there was a DDoS attack on top ISPs in Cambodia includes EZECOM, Digi, SINET, and Telcotech were attacked by unknown hacker group with no ransom demands. It almost reached 150Gbps that cause cutdown the internet access almost a whole day across the country (Pascu, n.d.). Other considerations are the highly price technologies that need highly financial budget as well. It is very difficult for developing country like Cambodia. Servers, computers, CCTV cameras, and other devices are needed in large numbers and their prices are not cheap. All devices of smart city development are also needed the high speed Internet and stable and enough electricity. What will happen if the internet speed is unstable or cutdown, how devices or data can be communicated to each other. Beside internet speed, if there is no stable electricity how smart city works.

2.2. Evaluates potential solutions of smart city

After evaluating the potential solutions of smart city, there are some points to consider related to security, data protection, monitoring and analyzing suspicious activities, and so on. Smart city must be improved by high security and data protection from cyberattacks. It needs a large number of budgets to invest a strong cybersecurity ecosystem to make it becomes a robust smart city. Data storage must be encrypted, use the Safeguard mechanism protection, or update operating system and application regularly. Hire or create a strong security engineering teams by red team do the penetration testing or similar security scanning activities to detect and manage vulnerabilities in the systems. And blue team identifies the possible vulnerabilities to defense and strengthen the systems. All parties must process multi-layered approach to security which related to monitoring and analyzing to detect suspicious activity traffic or threats before their attacking. Make up everything is manageable to avoid the case of DDoS attack as seen in the 2018 Cambodia's ISP cyberattack. Another consideration is data privacy, so it needs to create a clear guidelines and regulations involve with collection, and sharing personal or confidential data. Smart cities must prioritize transparency by announcing about the data collected, how to use it and who has access to users or citizens, make sure that they have awareness about the data privacy. Providing users options to control and manage their own data by the ability to remove options of monitoring or sharing their privacy data. In the A case like this was reported in 2024 in Cambodia, there was a CoolApp, an instant message platform which the company does not store user's data. users must store their data on their own devices. Confidence and security must be enhanced and implement to data protection polices strictly. Regarding energy security, smart cities should invest in resilient and diverse energy sources. This includes developing backup power systems and exploring renewable energy options to reduce reliance on a single power supply. To ensure that power infrastructure is robust and flexible to better withstand problems and maintain their smart capabilities even during power outages. For internet connection consideration is not much different from the energy, smart city must find multiple connection resource for backing up connection. The speed must be fast enough to supports smart city and work simultaneously. If there is a question to ask how much to develop a smart city, so it is not easy to answer, finding supporters, increasing national income or borrowing money from foreign partners to spend on smart city development. It is not only expense but it is the return on

investment. Top 5 smartest country as mention above and most of the developed country already implemented the smart city because they its advantage to make their country more prosperous.

2.3. Ethical frameworks and principles in data science

As stated by Atlan (2023), “Data ethics is becoming increasingly significant as organizations rely more on data analytics and artificial intelligence to drive decision-making. Here are the key principles of data ethics: Transparency, Consent, Fairness and equity, Privacy protection, Accountability, Data minimization, Continuous monitoring and improvement, and Stakeholder engagement. Data ethics revolves around the responsible and morally sound management of data. As data plays an ever-larger role in our lives and businesses, an ethical framework becomes imperative to ensure trust, accountability, and fairness. These include: Data collection, Data storage, Data usage, Data sharing, Data accuracy, Individual rights, Openness and accountability, Ongoing education and training, Transparency in automated decision-making, and Stakeholder collaboration.” There are some examples of data science ethics include data release by OK Cupid published unethical a dataset of more than 70 thousand users of online dating platform in 2016. Additionally, Data Breach by American financial services company Robinhood in 2021 that the system was exploited to receive email accounts, names, and contact information more than 5 million users of the trading platform.

3. Legal Considerations

3.1. Legal considerations related to smart city

For smart city in Cambodia, relevant laws, regulations, and policies are received from a variety of sources include Urban Development and Planning Policies, Data Privacy and Protection Laws, Cybersecurity Regulations, Technology and Innovation Policies. Cambodia’s Vision 2030 Policy is one of other policies of Urban Development and Planning Policies aims at a goal where all Cambodians will enjoy comprehensive protection and support across all stages of life, moving towards a social protection floor for all (*Vision 2030: A Society of Care and Security for All in Cambodia*, n.d.). The National Strategic Development Plan (NSDP) 2019-2030 has been formulated to implement the Rectangular Strategy to ensures development sustainability and poverty reduction. The implement components are growth, employment, equity and efficiency

(FAOLEX, n.d.). Based on Data Protection Guide Cambodia, however data protection law has not yet been enacted in Cambodia but e-commerce law also can be used to be a law to protect user privacy data and restrict digital data protection with key data protection principles are lawfulness, specific purpose, purpose limitation, accurate, and security and confidentiality. The e-commerce law is supervised by ministry of commerce, ministry of post and telecommunications, and ministry of interior (*Data Protection Guide Cambodia*, n.d.). All commercial and civil acts, documents, and transactions executed via an electronic system are subject to the E-commerce Law unless they are related to powers of attorney, wills and successions, or real estate. Recently drafted cybersecurity legislation has been provided by Ministry of Post and Telecommunications and refined by two international human rights NGOs. (*Concerns Over Draft Cyber Law Allayed by Official Explanation*, n.d.). For Digital Economy and Society Policy Framework and National ICT Policy are the main parts of Technology and Innovation Policies. Digital economy and society policy framework is building to improve digital sectors and transform in all parties to have awareness with technologies especially smart city. All parties that involve including the country, city, government, citizens, and private businesses or NGOs to increase new economic growth and promote social welfare in the new normal. The objectives of National ICT Policy to achieve are providing ICT legal framework for every citizen and key stakeholders and enhancing the awareness the potential of ICT role firstly in sustainable development, secondly in the empowerment of people and third in enhancing governance.

3.2. Evaluates potential solutions to legal frameworks related to data science

To address the challenges faced by smart cities in Cambodia, several potential solutions can be proposed to enhance security, data privacy and protection, and overall effectiveness while aligning with existing laws and regulations. The legal frameworks such as Cambodia's Vision 2030 Policy and National Strategic Development Plan (NSDP) 2019-2030 solves the smart city issues by prioritizing high strong cybersecurity sector to avoid and protect against cyberattacks. It also supports all of these demands by concentrating on awareness of data protection and sustainable development. Because of the limitation or no specific data protection in Cambodia, e-commerce law can be used by many ministries to implement cybersecurity legislation. Cybersecurity sectors include red team group and blue team group work involving for system

attack testing and system defense and implement multi-layered security approach. This strategy needs a strong legal framework that support to develop clear regulations for data privacy protection and cybersecurity. To address this challenge, smart cities should invest in resilient diverse energy sources and internet connection. For his includes developing backup power systems and exploring renewable energy options to reduce reliance on a single power supply. Theses solutions align with the Digital Economy and Society Policy Framework and the National ICT Policy that aim to supports digital awareness of role in technology and infrastructure.

Conclusion

Awareness of ethical and legal issues related to data science is very important for IT engineer or Data Scientist because it helps them to research and analyze ethical considerations on a new project or existing project that they are working on to find the potential solutions aligns to the legal frameworks. For smart city in Cambodia may leverage the advantages of smart city while preserving individual rights and advancing moral behavior by taking proactive measures to address these issues. To plan, implement and sustainable the smart city project, cybersecurity, data privacy protection, electricity and internet connection are raised for considerations and potential solutions. And all of these solutions must be aligned to the laws or regulation under management by Cambodia's government.

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ITDS660 - Assignment Rubric

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Category	Marks Allocation	Marks Attained	Comments
1. Research and Analysis	40 marks	30	
2. Ethical Considerations	30 marks	22	
3. Legal Considerations	20 marks	15	
4. Writing and Presentation	10 marks	7	
<p>*** Penalty *** This penalty is for papers that do not meet the assignment requirements. (i.e. word count, format, etc.)</p>	(-5)		
Total marks allocated and achieved:	100 marks	74	